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A gradient elastic homogenisation model for brick masonry

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ABSTRACT

The elastic macro-mechanical properties of masonry are investigated herein by taking into account the presence of a weakly non-local heterogeneity within a simple gradient elasticity model. Masonry has a heterogeneous structure composed of masonry units bound by mortar. The homogenisation of masonry walls is a challenging task but also a very appealing method for modelling heterogeneity effects exhibited by masonry elements. In particular, it allows the use of smeared mechanical properties, thus avoiding the need of knowing the exact unit-to-unit and joint-to-joint geometry. Current codes provide very simplified empirical expressions to estimate an isotropic elastic modulus of masonry on the basis of its strength properties. The respective equations which do not take into account the anisotropy of masonry, present high scatter resulting in ambiguous safety. The homogenization argument employed in this work is based on a simple procedure utilising Aifantis' gradient elasticity (GradEla) model. The GradEla model is a straight-forward extension of Hooke's law by enhancing it with the addition of the Laplacian of the classical expression of the Hookean stress multiplied by an internal length accounting for the local heterogeneity. It has been successfully used to eliminate singularities from dislocation lines and crack tips, as well as in interpreting size effects. However its use in masonry structures has not yet been explored. A first step in this direction is attempted in this paper with emphasis on obtaining practical easy-to-use results rather than exhausting all other possibilities and complexities encountered in GradEla and its generalisation, as well as in more involved homogenisation procedures. In our analysis uniform vertical, horizontal and shear loads are assumed to act on the boundaries of the representative volume/surface element. The components of masonry are assumed to follow a gradient elastic stress distribution resulting in a gradient elastic homogenised model (GREHM). GREHM comprises a set of closed-form concise equations which estimate the elastic moduli in the longitudinal and transverse directions, the shear modulus and the Poisson's ratio. The aforementioned orthotropic material properties are verified using experimental results and also, compared to other homogenisation models. The validation shows that the proposed equations can effectively estimate with considerable precision the elastic properties of masonry walls. To illustrate the resulting estimation of the orthotropic elastic properties, normalised graphs are provided.

1. Introduction

Masonry structures exhibit inherently low deformation capacity and present high vulnerability to earthquakes [1,2] requiring, therefore, special attention in their design. Masonry is a composite anisotropic material made of brick units and mortar joints which can be fairly well treated as an orthotropic material in the linear range of their performance. The design of new masonry structures, or the assessment of existing ones, needs reliable and robust models. The elastic moduli of masonry material are of outmost importance for the estimation of deformations and displacements using either elastic models which is the

most common case for the design (e.g. modal and spectral analysis for seismic loading with global behaviour factor), or inelastic ones which is the most common case for assessment purposes.

The mechanical properties of masonry structures built in-situ without pre-fabrication (Fig. 1) present a large discrepancy depending on the variety of materials, bonding of the bricks, geometries, and other arrangements related to the craftsmanship of masons. Masonry material is, in fact, a multiphase continuum comprising variations, discontinuities, cracks and interfaces. In view of the real nature of the material during service, detailed discrete micro-models considering the exact arrangement of masonry units and mortar joints along with their

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Nomenclature

A_x, A_y, A_ξ	cross-section area perpendicular to the axis x, y, ξ
A_s	shear cross-section area
b	bond
C_{ijkl}	material elastic modulus fourth order tensor
E	elastic modulus
$E_{b,x}, E_{b,y}$	hollow brick elastic modulus in horizontal, vertical direction
E_c	RSE core elastic modulus
E_{exp}	elastic modulus experimentally measured
E_h	homogenised elastic modulus in horizontal direction
E_m	elastic modulus of mortar
E_v	homogenised elastic modulus in vertical direction
E_v'	vertical homogenised elastic modulus using the 'exact' arrangement
e	error
F_{bx}	horizontal spring forces in brick units
F_{mx}	horizontal spring forces in mortar bed joints
F_x	force in x axis
F_y	force in y axis
f_{exp}	compressive strength experimentally measured
f_{mc}	compressive strength of masonry
G	homogenised shear modulus
G_b	shear modulus of brick units
G_m	shear modulus of mortar joints
K_E	coefficient of elastic modulus
$k_{b,s}$	brick shear stiffness
$k_{b,x}, k_{b,y}$	Stiffness of bricks in x, y directions
k_c	RSE core stiffness
$k_{mb,x}$	stiffness of mortar bed joints in horizontal direction
$k_{mh,x}, k_{mh,y}$	stiffness of the mortar head joints in x, y directions

$k_{m,s}$	mortar shear stiffness
$k_{m,y}$	stiffness of mortar joints in y direction
$k_{h,s}$	homogenised shear stiffness
$k_{h,x}, k_{h,y}$	homogenised stiffness in x, y direction
k_ξ	axial stiffness
L_ξ	length along axis ξ
L_ξ^*	"Gradient" length L_ξ
ℓ	internal length
N_ξ	axial Load
p	external distributed load on the wall
T	spatial vector of periodic dimensions
$t_{b,x}, t_{b,y}$	horizontal and vertical dimension of bricks
$t_{m,x}, t_{m,y}$	head and bed joint mortar thickness
$t_{tot,x}, t_{tot,y}$	total thickness of RSE in x, y direction
u	axial displacement
V	shear force
w	wall thickness
Γ_d	FE model
Γ_h	GREHM model
γ	shear strain
δ_x, δ_y	local displacements at the boundaries in x and y axis
Δ_x, Δ_y	horizontal and vertical displacement
ε_{kl}	strain tensor
ε_ξ	axial strain
ν_b	Poisson's ratio of solid bricks
ν_m	Poisson's ratio of mortar
ν_{yx}, ν_{xy}	Poisson's ratios of homogenised masonry
$\nu_{b,xy}, \nu_{b,yx}$	Poisson's ratios of orthotropic (hollow) bricks
σ_{ij}	stress tensor
σ_x, σ_y	normal stress in x, y axis
σ_ξ	spring axial stress
τ	shear stress

distinct properties and those of the interfaces have been proposed. Due to their complexity, however, their use is only limited to element-wise (local) analysis and they are neither feasible, nor applicable, especially for the design of buildings [3], or building aggregates [4,5] since the computational effort is very high and the exact units and mortars geometry difficult to be accurately defined and meshed. The commonly applied design methods are based on homogenised macro-mechanical properties of masonry utilising either shell or beam elements, i.e. the well-known equivalent frame model, to describe the global behaviour of masonry structures [3,6–11]. In the first place, the elastic moduli are needed for modelling masonry walls. The current codes, however, do not include physically-based or theoretically-deduced estimates. Instead, estimates of the elastic moduli of masonry walls are used based

on either wallette experiments or, on empirical formulas involving the wallette compressive strength which in turn is also given by an empirical formula. As already mentioned [12] and will also be shown herein, such an approach typically results in large discrepancies. Clearly the consideration of a perfectly homogeneous and isotropic material with a single adjustment of the elastic modulus, as described above, is far from being a realistic assumption.

The aforementioned current design practice can thus be attributed to the complexity of the problem and the heretofore models (a considerable number of parameters needs to be defined), as well as to the fact that homogenisation procedures are based on the elastic properties of the masonry constituents materials which are not always provided. However, it should be noted that the moduli of elasticity are derived

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. Masonry walls arrangements: (a) periodic and (b) non-periodic.

from the same compressive tests, i.e. no additional effort is needed. It follows that the lack of sufficient information on the moduli of elasticity of brick units and mortar stems from the current design standards which allow estimating masonry's modulus empirically, based on its compression strength. Interestingly, for existing structures standard penetration tests are easier to perform than a flat jack test to estimate the elastic properties of bricks and mortar [13]. Given that the current proposed empirical equations for the elastic properties of masonry have high variability and an ambiguous safety factor, it is of great importance to explore new methods for obtaining better and more reliable equations for the elastic properties of masonry. An alternative promising approach is to use homogenisation techniques which can result in micromechanically-based estimates of the effective linear elastic properties of heterogeneous periodic materials [14] such as of the brick structure of Fig. 1a. The first step in homogenisation procedures is to identify the representative volume/surface element (RVE/RSE) of the macrostructure and then, to formulate the kinematics of every constituent part, which together with the boundary conditions are solved to estimate the macro-mechanical properties by averaging the resulting stress field over the RVE [15–23]. A basic assumption is that the RVE is small enough compared to the total size of the structure so that scale effects are negligible. Even though such homogenisation procedures are mathematically rigorous, they are usually complex and not attractive to practitioners to use. Moreover, they usually neglect the presence of high local gradients, emerging from heterogeneities and at interfaces. A different approach which accounts for local strain gradients and related size effects is considered in the present article. It is based on Aifantis gradient elasticity (GradEla) theories which have been widely used in recent years to model heterogeneity effects in elastic microstructures and small volumes (RVE/RSE). A recent comprehensive review of GradEla and its applications is given in [24] which focuses on its ability to eliminate elastic singularities from dislocation lines and crack tips. Even though other applications of GradEla in modelling size effects on beams have been considered [25,26] its use in masonry structures has not been explored. This is the purpose of the present article. In particular, the weakly nonlocal or internal length gradient (ILG) parameter of GradEla is used to adjust the effective elastic simple single dimensional analysis. This is in contrast to existing homogenisation schemes applied to masonry as is briefly reviewed in this paper. More specifically, the problem of deducing a rather accurate elastic modulus for masonry is tackled by adopting a comprehensive but also practical and straightforward approach based on the GradEla model and its non-local ILG. In principle the ILG can take into account size effects, as well as local phenomena during service such as the presence of shrinkage cracks and voids. In modelling masonry or masonry-like (i.e. multi-phase brittle) structures the ILG is introduced to account for heterogeneous effects due to different bond arrangements and other surface-related phenomena [27–31]. By incorporating this parameter for the first time in a homogenisation masonry model, a set of closed-form expressions is deduced for the elastic orthotropic moduli which are calibrated against numerical models and experimental results. These expressions, which are applied in one step avoiding cumbersome finite element analyses, are compared to other homogenisation schemes. It is shown that the present model can estimate with higher precision the corresponding values obtained from experimental results and furthermore, has the merit of a more general and at the same time simpler form. It is readily applicable requiring only the elastic properties of masonry units and mortar (i.e. the elastic moduli and the Poisson's ratios) and their dimensions. Normalised graphs are provided to illustrate the estimation of the orthotropic properties for various ranges and a proposal for the internal length parameter is made.

2. A model with an internal non-local length for a 1-d element

Classical elasticity theory is extensively used in a wide range of design problems and applications in civil engineering. However, it fails

to represent local heterogeneity phenomena and cannot take into consideration size effects which appear as structural size decreases, as well as to dispense with elastic singularities such as those occurring during the application of point loads or, those appearing at dislocation lines and crack tips [32]. The aforementioned deficiencies of classical elasticity can be attributed to the absence of an internal length parameter in the constitutive equations to characterise the local heterogeneity and microstructure-induced spatial gradients [33,34]. To remedy the situation, a vast literature has been developed on generalised elasticity theories starting effectively with the brothers Cosserat (to note only some recent references on their theory [15,35–39]) continuing in the 60s with Toupin [40], Mindlin [41,42] and Eringen [43] among others and revitalised in the early 90s by Aifantis more attractive and easy-to-use GradEla model. This is the simplest model that is proposed here to be used in masonry building codes and employed in the design process of masonry construction projects. In doing so, several simplifications concerning the structure and the theory (constant internal length, same value in tension/compression and shear) will be adopted and the delicate problem of boundary conditions will be addressed in the basis of simple physically-based grounds consistent with the experiments, rather than more general mathematical considerations based on variational principles. In view of the above we proceed by summarising the basics of the GradEla model. This proposes to incorporate into the classical linear elastic constitutive relation of strain ε_{kl} and stress σ_{ij} of the continuum media the Laplacian of the strain [44,45]. Assuming a general elastic material the enhanced constitutive elasticity law between the stress σ_{ij} and the strain ε_{kl} tensors becomes as follows:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}(\varepsilon_{kl} - \ell^2 \nabla^2 \varepsilon_{kl}) \quad (1)$$

where C_{ijkl} is the material elastic moduli fourth order tensor and ℓ is the internal non-local length. Generalisations of the above relationship (e.g. different ℓ values for axial and shear deformations) are possible but for simplicity, the initial GradEla model is assumed where ℓ is a constant and this approximation is used here in exploring the applicability of GradEla to masonry structures. The larger the ℓ is, the wider is the area affected by the local developed strain gradients. Next, an axial single degree of freedom (SDOF) gradient elastic spring is assumed with cross-section area A_ξ and length L_ξ along the longitudinal axis ξ (Fig. 2).

The considered element is assumed fixed at the one side ($\xi = 0$) and free at the end ($\xi = L_\xi$) where the axial load N_ξ is applied. In this case Eq. (1) is simplified to

$$\sigma_\xi = E \left(\varepsilon_\xi - \ell^2 \frac{d^2 \varepsilon_\xi}{d\xi^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

where ε_ξ is the spring axial strain, $\sigma_\xi = N_\xi/A_\xi$ is the spring axial stress and E is the spring elastic modulus. Given that the elastic strain is the derivative of the displacement $\varepsilon_\xi = du/d\xi$, Eq. (2) can be written as

$$\frac{N_\xi}{A_\xi} = E \left(\frac{du_\xi}{d\xi} - \ell^2 \frac{d^3 u_\xi}{d\xi^3} \right) \quad (3)$$

The above third order differential equation is solved for the displacement field $u(\xi) = u_\xi$, to give

Fig. 2. Axial 1-D gradient elastic element.

$$u_\xi = p_1 + p_2 e^{\frac{\xi}{\ell}} + p_3 e^{-\frac{\xi}{\ell}} + \frac{\xi \cdot N_\xi}{E \cdot A_\xi} \quad (4)$$

In Eq. (4) the first three terms of the right hand side represent the solution of the homogeneous equation where p_k , $k = \{1-3\}$ are three constants to be determined, and the fourth term is the particular solution. Kinematic consistent boundary conditions (Eqs. (5)) are considered to estimate the constants; one classical condition, the displacement; two non-classical ones, the second derivative of it at the fixed end and the other based on the vanishing of the displacement derivative at the free end [32,46–52]:

$$\begin{aligned} u_0 &= 0 \\ \frac{d^2 u_0}{d\xi^2} &= 0 \\ \frac{du_\xi}{d\xi} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5a,b,c)$$

It thus follows that,

$$\begin{aligned} p_1 &= 0 \\ p_2 = -p_3 &= -\frac{N_\xi \ell}{EA_\xi} \frac{1}{2 \cosh\left(\frac{L_\xi}{\ell}\right)} \end{aligned} \quad (6a,b,c)$$

By substituting Eq. (6a,b,c) in Eq. (4), the displacement and axial force at the free end ($\xi = L_\xi$) are expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} u_\xi &= \frac{N_\xi L_\xi}{EA_\xi} \left[1 - \frac{\ell}{L_\xi} \tanh\left(\frac{L_\xi}{\ell}\right) \right] \\ N_\xi &= \frac{EA_\xi}{L_\xi} \left[1 - \frac{\ell}{L_\xi} \tanh\left(\frac{L_\xi}{\ell}\right) \right]^{-1} \cdot u_\xi \end{aligned} \quad (7a,b)$$

Thus, the axial stiffness k of the gradient elastic spring is given:

$$\begin{aligned} k_\xi &= \frac{EA_\xi}{L_\xi^*} \\ L_\xi^* &= L_\xi \left[1 - \frac{\ell}{L_\xi} \tanh\left(\frac{L_\xi}{\ell}\right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (8a,b)$$

In Eq. (8a) L_ξ^* is the respective effective ‘gradient’ quantity of the length L_ξ of the spring given by Eq. (8b). Obviously, the classical elastic spring and the gradient one differ only in the estimation of the spring length, i.e. the former’s length L is the actual length of the spring, while the effective length L_ξ^* is given by a simple expression involving the ratio of the internal length ℓ to the geometric length L_ξ .

Following the same procedure, a gradient elastic shear spring can be established starting from Eq. (2) and considering only shear stresses and strains for a shear element with dimensions $L \times H$, with y being the vertical axis. Denoting τ the shear stress, γ the shear strain, A_s the shear cross section and G the shear modulus, the respective equations for the gradient elastic shear strain are:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau &= G \left(\gamma - \ell^2 \frac{d^2 \gamma}{dy^2} \right) \\ k_s &= \frac{GA_s}{H^*} \\ H^* &= H \left[1 - \ell \tanh\left(\frac{H}{\ell}\right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (9a,b,c)$$

where the shear strain is as usual equal to $\gamma = du/dy$.

It should be noted that other types of boundary conditions (Eq. (5)) could have been selected, see for example [48,51–53], which eventually would lead to a variation in the displacement field along the bar (Eq. (7a)) and therefore, to a different estimation of the axial stiffness k_ξ of the gradient elastic spring (Eq. (8a)). However, in line with the objective of this paper these are addressed on the basis of simple physical grounds at the support consistent with experiments, rather than the more general mathematical considerations which are based on variational principles or the consideration of additional internal lengths. Several displacement-force expressions were obtained in [54,55] based on different combinations of non-classical boundary conditions of vanishing and non-zero first and second derivative of displacement

imposed at the bar supports. These were based on the principle of virtual work such as those used in Altan and Aifantis [36], Altan et al. [56] and Ru and Aifantis [48], and other arbitrary ones. For the combination of the two non-classical boundary conditions used in the present paper, the displacement and stiffness observed showed a more modest behaviour with average estimated values, hence the choice in this paper. It should be noted that the boundary conditions used in Tsepoura et al. [52], differ slightly with the inclusion of the effect of the surface elastic strain energy and an additional material length. However, the significance of such an effect does not affect the intent of the model.

Gradient theories offer a robust way to account for size effects, eliminate singularities and remedy associated problems of mesh-size dependence in finite elements. The weakly nonlinear and damage/micro-crack has been shown to be accounted by the gradient term and evaluated through the internal length parameter [57]. Thus, it is chosen to focus on a simple phenomenological interpretation of the internal length in accordance with experimental observation for the structural confirmation at hand. The internal length ℓ represents the underlying local phenomena and depends on the controlling micro and meso scale features such as shrinkage crack, void, porosity and mortar particle size. Hence it is not merely a numerical method but rather a physically-based procedure to account for local heterogeneity and gradient effects. In the case of masonry, obviously the connection between the constituent parts is not perfect. Mortar when applied cannot cover in a ‘homogeneous’ manner the brick units, and hence voids and shrinkage cracks appear. Therefore, in the elastic range and for low levels of compressive loading these cracks tend to close leading to a departure from linear elastic response resulting among other things, to an increasing elastic modulus in the elastic range [58]. The internal length used here may be viewed as a simple method to represent the extent of these early loading phenomena, within an extended gradient elasticity framework.

3. Formulation of the gradient elastic homogenised model (GREHM)

3.1. Homogenisation methods overview

One of the first attempts for the homogenisation of masonry was made by Pande et al. [59], who proposed a stepwise procedure: in the horizontal direction the masonry units and the head mortar joints are homogenised and then, in the vertical direction this part is further homogenised taking into account the bed mortar joints. A rationale for the homogenisation technique in masonry structures was established by Anthoine [19] who provided a rigorous mathematical framework. Based on that work and the definition of RVE, several other methods have been proposed in the sequel. These can be grouped in two broad categories: (i) those based on the analytical solution of the governing equilibrium equations and, (ii) those based on the numerical solution of the governing equations. The former approaches result in closed form expressions while the latter need a stepwise procedure. For instance, a set of equations to be solved, based on the loads, deformations and boundary conditions around the RVE, have been proposed in [21,22,60,61]. The analytical homogenisation is based on certain assumptions on the kinematics of the RVE to simplify the equilibrium equations at the interconnected brick and mortar elements. An approach which can provide more practical tools for engineering applications assumes the various constituents to comprise a set of homogeneous interconnected media modelled by classical elasticity e.g. [62–65]. Adopting a ‘fibre model’ and treating each axis of the RVE independently while neglecting lateral strains, it provides a further simplification [62,66,67] which, however, leads to a decreased elastic modulus especially in the case of higher Poisson ratios such as those appearing in the non-linear range in the case of damaged masonry as reported in [64]. On the other hand, to tackle issues related to scale and crack emergence phenomena, a higher order continuum has been

considered for the “heterogeneous” RVEs and corresponding properties were derived in a multi-step analysis [30,37–39,68–70]. The numerical methods, on the other hand, solve the local equilibrium problem by means of finite element (FE) models [19,71,72] and have the merit that can be adapted to any geometry. However, they fail to yield closed-form solutions.

The homogenisation procedure has been extended to masonries with non-periodic texture of bricks [73] such as that shown in Fig. 1b. Moreover, homogenisation has been applied to derive the out-of-plane properties based on the reduction of the mortar joints to contact interfaces with diagonal constitutive tensors and assuming the masonry as a thick plate [61,74]. Furthermore, results have been derived for the non-linear material properties using analytical solutions by means of strain energy considerations of limit analysis [75–81] which have also been extended to the non-linear regime [60,82]. Several such studies have been carried out in recent years and the reader is referred to state-of-the-art and review papers for further details [66,83,84].

3.2. Basic analytical considerations of GREHM

GREHM is developed for a running or a stack bond masonry but the methodology can be easily adapted to other masonry bonds. The representative element of the periodic masonry wall, which is the smallest repetitive cell, for these two bonds consists of one brick unit bounded by half thickness mortar joints as shown in Fig. 3. This element is repeated throughout a masonry wall excluding boundaries. The periods of the spatial variation of the medium T in the 2D dimensional space are equal to the respective dimensions of the representative surface element (RSE), namely the length and height of the brick and the mortar joint, respectively, i.e. $T = [(t_{m,x} + t_{b,x}) (t_{m,y} + t_{b,y})]^T$ (see also Fig. 3). The geometric and mechanical properties of masonry represented by the function \mathcal{F} fulfill the regular periodicity rule for composite media [14]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}[\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{N}(b) \cdot \mathbf{T}] &= \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{x}) \\ \mathbf{x} &= \begin{bmatrix} x_i \\ y_j \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{N}(b) &= \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, & b = 1 \\ \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, & b = 2 \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

In Eq. (10) \mathbf{x} is the coordinates vector of a certain i point, T is the

period vector and \mathbf{N} matrix depends on the bond $b = \{1 \text{ for running bond}, 2 \text{ for stack bond}\}$. It should be noted that the geometry of the RSE presents a double symmetry in the horizontal and vertical axes.

On the boundary of the RSE a uniform stress distribution is assumed which is valid for gravity loads. For dynamic loads the spatial stress variation is assumed very small and neglected in the RSE as normally the vector T will be very small with respect to the total dimensions of the wall. For the elastic response of the RSE the mortar joints are considered fully interconnected to the brick unit and no sliding is taken into account. Moreover, the thickness of the wall is assumed very thin compared to the other dimensions and the wall as a plane 2-D element. In the following elastic analysis the assumption that plane sections remain plane after deformation is also made and the Poisson effect is neglected. Based on gradient elasticity and these assumptions, the RSE is equivalent to a set of springs for the constitutive components respectively; brick units, mortar head and bed joints. The dimensions of the RSE are shown in Fig. 3b. The thickness of mortar joints is denoted as $t_{m,x}$ for head joints and $t_{m,y}$ for bed joints. The brick units have dimensions $t_{b,x}$ and $t_{b,y}$ in the horizontal and vertical direction, respectively. A raised asterisk (*) is used in the following to denote the gradient quantity of the respective dimension according to Eq. (8b).

The elastic modulus of mortar is denoted as E_m whereas hollow brick units generally present an orthotropic behaviour having two elastic moduli $E_{b,x}$ and $E_{b,y}$ in the two directions (solid units are isotropic). The Poisson's ratios are for mortar ν_m and for the orthotropic bricks $\nu_{b,xy} = \nu_{b,yx} E_{b,x} / E_{b,y}$. The gradient elastic stiffness of the axial and shear springs representing the masonry elements is estimated according to Eqs. (8a) and (9a). The same notation applies to the horizontal and vertical stiffnesses of mortar $k_{m,x|y}$ and bricks $k_{b,x|y}$, respectively.

3.3. Homogenised masonry elastic modulus E_v perpendicular to mortar bed joints (vertical)

For the estimation of the homogenised elastic modulus E_v in the vertical direction perpendicular to mortar bed joints a simplification on RSE is possible: it is sufficient to consider only the bed joints assuming that the load is uniformly distributed and $t_{m,x} < t_{b,x}/10$ (see Fig. 4). The difference in the elastic moduli of the actual RSE and the simplified one is very small depending on the properties of the masonry and the internal length (see Appendix). Thus, the homogenised vertical stiffness

Fig. 3. The representative surface element (RSE) of running bond brickwork: (a) on the wall, (b) a close-up.

Fig. 4. Stress distribution in RSE for the elastic modulus in the vertical direction and respective spring configuration.

$k_{h,y}$ using the spring configuration of the composite material shown in Fig. 4 and the gradient elastic stiffness (Eq. (8)) of the constituent parts is:

$$k_{h,y} = \frac{k_{b,y}k_{m,y}}{2k_{b,y} + k_{m,y}} \quad (11)$$

A unitary thickness for the wall is assumed and Eqs. (8a,b) are considered for the estimation of the spring stiffness. Table 1 presents the parameters defining the stiffness of the spring components.

The homogenised modulus of elasticity E_v after substitution of the spring stiffnesses in Eq. (11) (parameters given in Table 1) and some algebraic calculation can be found:

$$E_v = t_{tot,y} \frac{E_{b,y}E_m}{2(t_{m,y}/2)^*E_{b,y} + t_{b,y}^*E_m} \quad (12)$$

where $t_{tot,y} = t_{b,y} + t_{m,y}$ is the total thickness of the representative volume in the respective direction.

3.4. Homogenised masonry elastic modulus E_h parallel to mortar bed joints (horizontal)

For the estimation of the homogenised elastic modulus E_h in the horizontal direction parallel to mortar bed joints the full RSE should be taken into consideration (Fig. 5) as the omission of the latter results in larger difference. Therefore, when the uniform stress σ_x is applied both the mortar head and bed joints are loaded. Due to strain compatibility and the interaction between mortar bed joints and the brick units the stress field becomes more complicated. A simplification is possible due to the small thickness of the mortar joints: the stress distribution in the bed joints is uniform. The closer to unity is the ratio E_b/E_m and the smaller the mortar thickness the more accurate is this assumption.

Based on the previous assumptions the spring configuration shown in Fig. 5 represents the stress field of the RSE. In terms of spring analysis, there is a central core of three springs in parallel: a spring representing the brick and two springs for the bed joints. Then, this core spring is connected in each side in row with a spring representing the head joint. The parameters for defining the spring elements stiffness are

presented in Table 2. The core spring has a stiffness k_c :

$$k_c = k_{b,x} + 2k_{mb,x}$$

$$E_c = \frac{E_{b,x}t_{b,y} + E_{m,x}t_{m,y}}{t_{b,y} + t_{m,y}} \quad (13a,b)$$

By analogy with Eqs. (11) and (12) the homogenised elastic stiffness $k_{h,x}$ and modulus in the horizontal direction E_h will be:

$$k_{h,x} = \frac{k_c k_{mh,x}}{2k_c + k_{mh,x}}$$

$$E_h = t_{tot,x} \frac{E_c E_m}{2(t_{m,x}/2)^*E_c + t_{b,x}^*E_m} \quad (14a,b)$$

where $t_{tot,x} = t_{b,x} + t_{m,x}$ is the total thickness of the representative volume in the horizontal direction.

3.5. Homogenised masonry shear elastic modulus G

The shear elastic modulus of the homogenised masonry is estimated using the gradient elasticity law of Eq. (9a). When the simplified RSE is loaded with a horizontal shear force V then in all the layers the same stress τ is developed (Fig. 6). Obviously, the total shear strain of the RSE is equal to the addition of the three element. A similar spring configuration to the vertical elastic modulus is assumed but in this case considering shear springs, as illustrated in Fig. 6.

It is noted that the shear springs are in row loaded by the same shear force V . As a result, Eqs. (11) and (12) are here transformed as follows:

$$k_{h,s} = \frac{k_{b,s}k_{m,s}}{2k_{b,s} + k_{m,s}}$$

$$G = t_{tot,y} \frac{G_b G_m}{2(t_{m,y}/2)^*G_b + t_{b,y}^*G_m} \quad (15a,b)$$

where $k_{i,s}$ is the shear stiffness of the respective element i and G_b and G_m are the shear elastic moduli of the brick unit and the mortar joints, respectively. The parameters of the shear springs stiffness are presented in Table 3.

3.6. Homogenised masonry Poisson's ratios ν_{xy} and ν_{yx}

The Poisson's ratio ν_{yx} is defined as the ratio of the horizontal dilatation to the vertical deformation for a vertical stress σ_{yy} of the RSE (Fig. 4) and can be expressed as:

$$\nu_{yx} = -\frac{\sigma_x E_v}{\sigma_y E_h} \quad (16)$$

The sign at the right hand side of Eq. (16) is minus because the developed stresses for classical materials have opposite signs. The horizontal E_h and the vertical E_v elastic moduli are given by Eqs. (14b) and (12), respectively, whereas the vertical stress is $\sigma_y = F_y/A_y = F_y/t_{b,y}$ and the horizontal stress $\sigma_x = F_x/A_x = F_x/(t_{b,y} + t_{m,y})$. The vertical springs are in series and thus, they carry an equal force: $F_y = F_{by} = F_{my}$. The total force F_x is proportionally divided in the parallel horizontal springs (Eq. (13a)) instead. The horizontal spring forces in the brick unit F_{bx} and mortar bed joints F_{mx} can be expressed in terms of the vertical force F_y (given that (a) the force is the product of the stiffness k times the respective displacement δ , (b) the displacement δ is the strain ϵ times the respective length L and, (c) the strains in the two orthogonal directions are related with the Poisson ratio ν), as follows:

Table 1
Parameters for the stiffness estimation of the springs in the vertical direction.

Element	Elastic modulus	Area A_y	'Gradient' length (L_y)*	Internal length	Stiffness
Brick	$E_{b,y}$	$t_{b,x} \times 1$	$(t_{b,y})^*$	ℓ	$k_{b,y}$
Mortar bed joints	E_m	$t_{m,x} \times 1$	$(t_{m,y}/2)^*$		$k_{m,y}$

Fig. 5. Masonry springs connection in the horizontal direction.

$$\begin{aligned} F_{bx} &= -v_b \frac{k_{b,x} t_{b,x}}{k_{b,y} t_{b,y}} F_y \\ F_{mx} &= -v_m \frac{k_{mb,x} t_{b,x}}{k_{m,y} t_{m,y/2}} F_y \end{aligned} \quad (17a,b)$$

where v_b and v_m are the Poisson's ratio of the brick unit and the mortar, respectively. In the case that the brick unit is a hollow brick with an orthotropic behaviour it will have two Poisson's ratios $v_{b,xy}$ and $v_{b,yx}$. Combining Eqs. (13a) and (17a,b) the ratio of the forces can be estimated as:

$$\frac{F_x}{F_y} = -v_b \frac{k_{b,x} t_{b,x}}{k_{b,y} t_{b,y}} - 2v_m \frac{k_{mb,x} t_{b,x}}{k_{m,y} t_{m,y/2}} \quad (18)$$

Therefore, combining Eqs. (16), (17a,b) and (18) it is concluded that:

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{yx} &= \frac{v_b t_{b,y}^* + 2v_m (t_{m,y/2})^*}{t_{b,x}^*} \frac{t_{b,x}}{t_{b,y} + t_{m,y}} \frac{E_b}{E_h} \\ \nu_{xy} &= \frac{v_b t_{b,y}^* + 2v_m (t_{m,y/2})^*}{t_{b,x}^*} \frac{t_{b,x}}{t_{b,y} + t_{m,y}} \end{aligned} \quad (19a,b)$$

4. Parametric analysis

A parametric investigation is carried out to explore the influence of the most important parameters which can affect the orthotropic behaviour of masonry: (i) the internal length which is an internal non-local parameter of the model, (ii) the mortar joints and especially their thickness and, (iii) the comparative stiffness of the brick units to the one of the mortar which are the main physical parameters. Normalised plots for the elastic moduli are then provided in Fig. 7, Fig. 8, Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 to facilitate the application of the method yielding results graphically.

The thickness of mortar joints influences the homogenised properties of masonry; the thicker the joints are, the more affected is the macro-behaviour of masonry. Moreover, the level of the influence depends on the mortar to brick modulus of elasticity ratio, E_m/E_b . A third parameter that controls the influence of mortar joints is the internal length. Apparently, the internal length is the physical measure that express the scale that a phenomenon (e.g. the presence of voids) in the

Table 2
Parameters for the stiffness estimation of the springs in the horizontal direction.

Element	Elastic modulus	Area A_x	'Gradient' length (L_x) [*]	Internal length	Stiffness
Brick	$E_{b,x}$	$t_{b,y} \times 1$	$(t_{b,x})^*$	ℓ	$k_{b,x}$
Mortar bed joints	E_m	$(t_{m,y/2}) \times 1$	$(t_{b,x})^*$		$k_{mb,x}$
Mortar head joint	E_m	$(t_{m,y} + t_{m,y}) \times 1$	$(t_{m,x/2})^*$		$k_{mh,x}$

micro-level tends to spread through. Given that mortar joints are commonly weaker and less stiff than brick units, they accommodate most of the local phenomena: cracking, slip etc. In the case that mortars are softer than bricks a triaxial stress state appears where mortar is confined laterally due to the stiffer surrounding bricks and shear stresses are developed in the interface boundary [85]. In the very early loading of compression tests the situation is non-linear [58]: micro cracks (e.g. shrinkage cracks) and voids in the interface are closing leading to a stiffer overall masonry response. In fact, this change of the stiffness properties of masonry buildings can also be seen in dynamic tests for very low magnitude loads [86]; the structure will still be in the elastic range of the response but there is a small change in the dynamic properties which implies the existence of cracks/dislocations in the interface between brick units and mortar joints, albeit invisible to the naked eye. Therefore, it is justified to relate the value of the internal length to the mortar joints thickness.

To this end, an analytical parametric analysis is carried out for various joint thicknesses (normalised to the brick height) assuming various elastic moduli ratios and various internal lengths. The range of the normalised thickness has been limited to $t_{my}/t_{by} = 0.5$ to reflect the most common masonries. It is noted that there are historical masonries (e.g. the roman ones) which have very thick mortar joints but the more contemporary ones rarely exceed the above limit. The influence of mortar joints in the vertical homogenised modulus is presented in Fig. 7 where the thickness is represented in the horizontal axis, the ratio of E_m/E_b in various lines (see legend of Fig. 7), and the internal length in successive plots. The normalised plots of the homogenised horizontal elastic modulus E_h and the homogenised shear modulus G are presented in Figs. 8 and 9, respectively. It is interesting to note that a soft mortar joint ($E_m/E_b = 0.25$) will affect the vertical elastic modulus up to a thickness $t_{my} = t_{by}$. Higher values of t_{my} will not have a significant impact on the mechanical properties which reach a stabilisation. This stabilisation thickness increases as the ratio E_m/E_b increases. Certainly, the ratio of E_m/E_b most predominantly rules the homogenised vertical modulus. However, the internal length is to limit this role. For example a value of internal length ℓ equal to the mortar joint thickness leads to a much lower impact of the ratio E_m/E_b on the homogenised elastic moduli.

In this parametric analysis common Poisson's ratios were assumed $v_b = 0.2$ for bricks and $v_m = 0.15$ for mortar and a ratio of the brick dimensions $t_{bx}/t_{by} = 3.25$ (which are the only fixed values that are included in these normalised graphs). The homogenised Poisson ratio ν_{yx} is presented in Fig. 10 for various joint thicknesses and various internal lengths. It is noted that for the above assumed values of Poisson ratios for the bricks and mortar the code value 0.25 is the upper bound limit in the elastic field. An increasing trend is observed for the Poisson ratio as the internal length increases. This increasing trend is stronger when the ratio of mechanical properties of the two materials (E_m/E_b) is lower and for smaller thicknesses of the joints (which is the common case). The homogenised Poisson's ratio ν_{xy} can then be easily estimated using the formula $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{yx} E_h/E_v$ (Eq. (19a,b)).

5. Comparison of GREHM with numerical models

The proposed model is compared with a FE based homogenisation model [19] to verify the proposed equations and confirm the assumptions of the model. Then, GREHM is applied on a two dimensional wall

Fig. 6. Masonry shear spring connection for shear force.

Table 3
Parameters for the stiffness estimation of the shear springs.

Element	Shear modulus	Area A_s	'Gradient' length (H) [*]	Internal length	Stiffness
Brick	G_b	$t_{b,x} \times 1$	$(t_{b,y})^*$	ℓ	$k_{b,s}$
Mortar bed joint	G_m	$t_{b,x} \times 1$	$(t_{m,y}/2)^*$		$k_{m,s}$

as a further numerical comparison to validate the efficiency at a larger scale. Apparently, the internal length in these FE comparisons is not playing a major role as the models are perfectly bonded and linear elastic apart from one case where the load creates a local singularity.

The actual efficiency of GREHM (and the internal length) will be shown in the next paragraph where the model is applied to masonry walls and wallets tested experimentally.

The wall used as a benchmark problem represents a specimen tested at the University of Patras [87]. The wall is 1.17 m long, 1.20 m high and 0.095 m thick with an aspect ratio close to unity. The in-plane dimensions of the homogeneous solid bricks are 0.195×0.060 m ($t_{b,x} \times t_{b,y}$) and the wall is single-leaf (i.e. the bricks are 0.095 m thick). The mortar thickness varies slightly in the two directions: $t_{m,x} = 0.0195$ m and $t_{m,y} = 0.0160$ m. The mechanical properties of the constituent materials needed for GREHM are summarised in Table 4. The shear moduli of brick units and mortar can be found 610 MPa and 290 MPa, respectively.

The application of GREHM is carried out as follows: (i) for the

Fig. 7. The (normalised) vertical elastic modulus E_v of masonry in respect to $t_{m,y}/t_{b,y}$ for various ratios of E_m/E_b and $\ell/t_{m,y}$.

Fig. 8. The (normalised) horizontal elastic modulus E_h of masonry in respect to t_{my}/t_{by} for various ratios of E_m/E_b and l/t_{my} .

estimation of the homogenised elastic moduli in the vertical E_v and the horizontal E_h directions, Eqs. (12) and (14b) are applied, respectively; (ii) for the estimation of the homogenised shear modulus G , Eq. (15b) is applied; (iii) finally for the estimation of the Poisson's ratio ν_{yx} and ν_{xy} , Eqs. (19a,b) are applied. As already mentioned in these equations the 'gradient' dimension $(\cdot)^*$ is given by Eq. (8b). A number of internal lengths are assumed ranging from 0 to t_{my} . The application of these equations and the influence of the internal length is depicted in Fig. 11. Obviously, it is a non-linear influence with an increasing trend for the elastic moduli and a decreasing one for the Poisson ratio.

The previous results of the homogenised properties are compared with purely elastic FE models of the RSE and the considered masonry wall implemented in Abaqus software [88]. In all the analyses the CPS4R four node plane stress element is used. The FEs representing the mortar joints and the bricks are fully connected between them (using nodal constraints) not allowing for any sliding at the interfaces.

5.1. Comparison of GREHM with a FE based homogenisation model

The estimation of the elastic properties of the considered wall is carried out using FE models [19]. To this end a RSE with a rectangular pattern for T (see also Fig. 3) is selected and is presented in Fig. 12, where red are the elements of brick units and orange those of the mortar. The mesh of the RSE is performed using rectangle (close to square) elements of size $8 \text{ mm} \times 8 \text{ mm}$ approximately. The selection of this RSE essentially simplifies the periodic conditions on the boundaries (PCBs) around the RSE to the following ones:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{x,right} - \delta_{x,left} &= \Delta_x \in \mathbb{R} \ \& \ \delta_{x,right} = 0 \\ \delta_{y,bottom} - \delta_{y,top} &= \Delta_y \in \mathbb{R} \ \& \ \delta_{y,bottom} = 0 \\ \delta_{y,right} - \delta_{y,left} &= \Delta_y \in \mathbb{R} \ \& \ \delta_{y,right} = 0 \\ \delta_{x,bottom} - \delta_{x,top} &= \Delta_x \in \mathbb{R} \ \& \ \delta_{x,bottom} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (20a,b,c,d)$$

where δ_x , δ_y are the displacements in x and y axis at the right, left, bottom and top boundaries of the RSE. The displacements $\Delta_x = 0.01 \text{ mm}$ and $\Delta_y = 0.01 \text{ mm}$ are applied to estimate the horizontal and vertical elastic modulus, E_h and E_v , and the Poisson's ratio ν_{xy} and ν_{yx} , respectively, using the PBCs given in Eqs. (20a,b). For the shear homogenised modulus G the PBCs expressed in Eqs. (20c,d) on the boundaries are applied with a horizontal displacement $\Delta_x = 0.01 \text{ mm}$. The deformations and the strain and stress states for this latter case are presented in Fig. 12. The results in terms of reaction forces (ΣF), stresses (σ , τ) and strains (ϵ , γ) of the RSE for all the loading cases, and the respective homogenised resulted orthotropic moduli of E_h , E_v and G and Poisson ratios ν_{xy} , ν_{yx} , are summarised in Table 5.

In the FE analysis of RSE the inclusion of the internal length l does not improve the accuracy. Comparing the results of Table 5 with those of GREHM presented in Fig. 11 it can be seen that for $l = 0$ there is an excellent match: $E_v = 1156.5 \text{ GPa}$, $E_h = 1168.8 \text{ GPa}$, $G = 495.34 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{xy} = 0.16$ and $\nu_{yx} = 0.16$ and the relevant differences 3%, 0%, 5%, 0% and 0%.

5.2. Influence of the internal length in numerical models

The influence of the internal length is also examined in a global analysis of a FE wall model. The wall is shown in Fig. 13a. The brick

Fig. 9. The (normalised) shear elastic modulus G of masonry in respect to t_{my}/t_{by} for various ratios of E_m/E_b and l/t_{my} .

pattern of the wall is not symmetric in the horizontal and the vertical direction: there are $5\frac{1}{2}$ bricks in the horizontal courses and 16 vertical courses in total (Fig. 13a).

A first FE model, called the 'distinct' one Γ_d , comprises different (classical) elastic plane elements for brick and mortar bed and head joints shown in Fig. 13b. The bricks have been meshed using 6×20 elements whereas the mortar using 2×20 and 8×2 elements for the bed and the head joints, respectively, using a mesh dimension approximately equal to $\frac{1}{2}$ of the mortar joint thickness. The elements are fully connected. The wall is restrained at its base to represent the experimental conditions.

At the second step of the investigation GREHM is applied and, therefore, the homogenised properties are used throughout the homogenised FE model $\Gamma_h(l)$, using various internal lengths l to compare its influence on the analysis.

The stress and deformed state of Γ_d FE model is presented in the left side of Fig. 14 for a number of different external loadings p : (i) an evenly distributed vertical load 100 kPa on the top (p_1), (ii) a lateral load of 100 kPa applied on the vertical left side of the wall (p_2) and, (iii) an in-plane moment produced by a vertical distributed load inverting sign at the middle of the wall, i.e. 100 kN/m and -100 kN/m at the top (p_3), all applied statically. The Von Mises stress state is presented in kPa. It can be observed that the brick units being the stiffer material attract higher stresses. This is more dominant in the first loading case.

Next, a second FE model Γ_h is run but in this case applying GREHM: all plane elements of Γ_h have the same homogenised properties. A number of internal lengths l ranging from 0 to 20 mm are assumed and hence, the respective models are generated $\Gamma_h(l)$. The same loads as previously are applied to all $\{\Gamma_h(l), l \in [0, 20 \text{ mm}]\}$. The stress and deformed state of $\Gamma_h(l = 0)$ are presented on the right of Fig. 14 where

it is seen that comparing the two stress states the homogenised model smooths out the distinct one.

A displacement approach is followed to compare the two models: the displacements of the model Γ_d with the distinct properties for the materials are assumed the correct values, and the error is estimated from the deviation of the respective displacements of the models with the GREHM properties $\Gamma_h(l)$ for the same loading conditions.

The error $e(l, p)$ between the nodal displacements j ($j = 1:n$) on the free boundaries of the distinct ($\delta_j^d(p)$) and the GREHM ($\delta_j^h(l, p)$) models is defined as follows:

$$e(l, p) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left| \frac{\delta_j^d(p) - \delta_j^h(l, p)}{\delta_j^d(p)} \right| \quad (21)$$

Therefore, the error $e(l, p)$ is defined as the averaged summation of the errors between the respective displacements of the two models, i.e. $e(l, p) = \sum_{j \in \Gamma} \epsilon_j$ for l, p and $\epsilon_j \in \Gamma$ where j is a node on the free boundary of the wall $S = \partial\Gamma_{\epsilon \neq 0}$.

In Fig. 15 the error $e(l, p)$ vs. the assumed internal length of each analysis for the three external loads p_1 , p_2 and p_3 is plotted. Interestingly the inclusion of the non-local length parameter can increase the accuracy of the analysis for the moment load. In fact, the application of a vertical load changing sign in the middle of the top side of the wall creates a local singularity. An internal length l around 4 mm can improve the estimation of the displacements in this case. For the other loading conditions the non-local parameter does not decrease the error. This would be expected for classical linear elastic FE models as has been already mentioned. For $l = 0$ the maximum error for all the loading conditions does not exceed 0.03%.

Fig. 10. The Poisson's ratio v_{yx} of masonry in respect to t_{my}/t_{by} for various ratios of E_m/E_b and l/t_{my} .

Table 4

Properties of brick units and mortar joints for GREHM.

	Size ($t_x \times t_y$) [m]	Elastic modulus (E) [GPa]	Poisson ratio (ν)
Brick units	0.195 × 0.060	1.4	0.15
Mortar joints	0.0195 × 0.0160	0.7	0.20

6. Experimental verification of GREHM and comparison with code and literature homogenisation models

6.1. Validation of GREHM and comparison with analytical models

A review of the closed-form homogenisation models can be found in [66]. Here a comparison is made between the proposed GREHM and three other models: the Pande et al. [59] model, and two recent models [62,66]. The code expression for the elastic modulus will be shown in a following section and compared with GREHM.

Experimental campaigns of masonry prisms and wallettes tested in vertical loading were collected from the literature. Herein those relevant tests that presented the material characterisation data needed for the application of GREHM, namely the mechanical properties of both the brick units and mortar, were selected and the relative experimental values of the vertical elastic modulus E_{exp} and the compressive strength f_{exp} are presented in Table 6 (ten different experimental campaigns resulted in 23 different masonry types). The validity of GREHM and the aforementioned homogenisation models is tested against these experimental results. The necessary data to apply all the models in the comparison are also given in Table 6. Moreover, the codes used to perform the compression tests (on mortar, bricks and masonry) are also

indicated. The calibrated value of l to achieve the highest possible consistency with the experimental values is also provided. Finally, the results of the vertical homogenised modulus E_v according to GREHM are also given in Table 6.

The comparison of the models is presented by means of the ratio between the analytical E_v to the experimental E_{exp} elastic modulus in the vertical direction (data given in Table 6), as illustrated in Fig. 16. The homogenised properties applying GREHM can be estimated fast using the normalised graphs of Figs. 7–9. It is noted that the limits of the vertical axis of Fig. 16 have been kept between 50% and 150% for better readability although a higher difference appeared in some cases. In general the proposed GREHM is more precise while the other models estimate lower values of the elastic modulus. The total error (i.e. root of the sum of squares over the total number of samples) across the 23 experimental tests is 0.74% for GREHM, 5.70% for [62], 5.47% for [66] and 5.22% for [59].

A correlation between the internal length l and the mortar physical properties is not straightforward since for most of the tests not all the properties have been measured. A very detailed experimental campaign in terms of physical properties measurements is the one made by Boffill et al. [90]. In this campaign historic masonries were tested consisting of solid clay bricks retrieved from traditional buildings and two types of lime mortars with different porosity were considered. According to the results, there is an apparent relation between the internal lengths adopted (Table 6) and the porosity: for the first three specimen types (BOF1 – BOF3) the internal length is almost half of the next series of specimens (BOF4 – BOF6) for which the porosity is approximately 50% higher.

As can be seen in Fig. 16 for the specimens HOS [93], NWO2 [95], RED1 [96] and VER [97] (see Table 6 for the details of the tests) all the

Fig. 11. The influence of the internal length normalised against the thickness of mortar joints on (a) the horizontal and vertical elastic moduli, (b) the shear modulus (normalised against the brick elastic modulus) and, (c) the Poisson’s ratio of the homogenised model.

models estimate very similar values. In particular for those tests the estimation of the internal length ℓ becomes minimum and a further comparison between the models is shown in Fig. 17 for the elastic modulus in the horizontal direction E_h , the shear modulus G and the Poisson ratio ν_{xy} . This is a purely analytical comparison of the homogenised values as these quantities had not been measured in relevant tests. As can be seen GREHM appears to give slightly higher values for E_v for the first three tests and for the fourth one it is [59] to be higher.

This tendency remains generally also for the other quantities apart from the shear modulus G where [66] increases. This comparison shows a general consistency between the models for these experiments.

6.2. Proposal of an ad-hoc internal length

The actual length of the non-local parameter varies for each masonry as can be seen in Table 6. Its length is related to the magnitude of

Fig. 12. The FE model of the RSE: (a) model, (b) shear displacements, (c) shear strain, and (d) shear stress.

Table 5
Results from the FE analysis of the RSE and homogenised mechanical properties.

Results & Homogenised properties		Units	Load direction		
			Horizontal	Vertical	Shear
Results from FEA	ΣF	kN	-787.34	1499.59	628.61
	$\varepsilon \mid \gamma$	-	4.66E-05	6.58E-05	6.58E-05
	ε (transversal)	-	7.61E-06	1.03E-05	-
	$\sigma \mid \tau$	GPa	-0.05	0.07	0.03
Homogenised properties	$E \mid G$	GPa	1169.55	1118.58	468.90
	$(E \mid G)/E_b$	-	0.84	0.80	0.33
	ν	-	0.16	0.16	-

the local phenomena that take place: it gets higher for mortars in traditional masonries with thicker joints which usually are based on lime without cement and have higher porosity. Therefore, a relationship for the estimation of the internal length should include the basic geometric and material properties of masonry (e.g. ratios $t_{m,x}/t_{b,x}$, E_m/E_b , etc. and porosity). The current group of tests give a narrow range of variation for these quantities and a correlation is not yet achievable. Instead, it can be stated that the internal length is related to the thickness of the mortar joints which are the weakest links in masonry and where normally most of the voids, cracks etc. initially exist. This can also be seen in Fig. 18 where the variation of the total error is plotted vs. relative internal length (i.e. the ratio of the internal length to the mortar thickness). This meaningful graph proposes a suggestion for the internal length when this cannot be known in advance;

$$\ell = 0.20 \cdot t_{m,x} \quad (22)$$

it can receive an optimum value 1/5 of the mortar joints thickness t_m (i.e. the value that minimises the error for the considered available data). Using this internal length the total error becomes larger, but less than 4.5%, which is still lower than those of the other models as shown in Fig. 18.

6.3. Evaluation of code expression and comparison with GREHM

Structural codes propose the following empirical relationship

Fig. 13. FEM of the wall: (a) the wall configuration, (b) mesh of the wall.

between the elastic modulus E and the compressive strength of masonry f_{mc} :

$$E = K_E \cdot f_{mc} \quad (23)$$

where K_E is a factor which can receive a value between 700 and 1000 depending on the type of masonry among various codes [108–111]. Experimental works, however, suggest that this value can range even more e.g. from $K_E = 250$ to $K_E = 1100$ approximately [90,112]. Moreover, it should be noted that the proposed elastic modulus assumes an isotropic behaviour and the Poisson's ratio is normally 0.25, resulting to a ratio of the shear to the elastic moduli $G/E = 0.4$. Therefore, it becomes very apparent that the code expression, although it has an intuitive justification, has a very high variability and its applicability is not well justified in experiments.

The comparison between the code expression of Eq. (23) and the GREHM using the ad hoc ℓ value is shown in Fig. 19. Moreover, the other homogenisation models are presented. The analytical and the experimental values have been normalised against the EC6 [108] value of the elastic modulus i.e. $1000f_{mc}$, while the lower limit $700f_{mc}$ of ACI530-11 [111] is also depicted (in which the compressive strength is the experimental one f_{exp}). Obviously, all the homogenisation models can be by far more accurate rather than the empirical estimation of the codes whose K_E factor should vary between 200 and 2500 approximately. In the most of the tests GREHM using the ad hoc value of the internal length ℓ is still more accurate.

Fig. 14. Comparison between the (Mises) stress field in kPa of the distinct-properties model Γ_d (on the left) and GREHM model Γ_h (on the right) for a vertical (a,b), horizontal (c,d) and moment (e,f) load.

Only very few experimental measurements of the elastic modulus lie between the limits of the code values (the two red dashed lines). At first glance the variability of the code expression is random and cannot be related to an actual trend. However, for the most tests (apart from the last four) the code expression give higher estimates of the elastic modulus compared to the experimental value, although this is an unconservative approach since it leads in turn to an estimation of lower deformations and displacements in the design process. Only the last

four tests (RED1 – RED4) of the bar graph (Fig. 19) using the code expressions result in lower estimates and refer to masonries with low strength brick units and thick joints. However, it can be stated that the code expression does not actually cover this kind of earth masonries. The code empirical expression is not recommended as it can generally lead to substantial differences of the elastic performance of masonry structures.

Fig. 15. The influence of the internal length on the accuracy of the model for three different loading conditions.

7. Conclusions

The elastic properties of masonry were investigated and a gradient elastic homogenisation orthotropic model (GREHM) was proposed for masonry brickwork to improve the code provisions for the elastic modulus. GREHM is a linear elastic orthotropic model for masonry brickwork. Current design codes, though they mainly propose linear

procedures for masonry design, they pay very basic attention to the elastic properties adopting an empirical expression which assumes an isotropic masonry material. The code relationship was compared to available experimental data and in some cases was found very unreliable, resulting in extremely large discrepancies as high as 400%. In the specimens studied herein, the code expression for the elastic modulus generally resulted to lower values; besides, its main inefficiency is related to the isotropic law assumed.

A set of closed-form expressions were proposed to estimate the in-plane elastic and shear moduli and the Poisson's ratios in two orthogonal directions. GREHM was developed introducing an internal non-local length to account for the micro-structure of multiphase masonry and the respective local phenomena that take place in reality in the identified RSEs for the horizontal and the vertical directions (i.e. parallel and perpendicular to the bed joints). The gradient elasticity was opted for it can take into account local scale phenomena appearing in multiphase materials such as voids in the discontinuities and stress concentration. The elastic stress field was analysed assuming a uniform load distribution and simplified stress distributions using gradient elastic springs.

The internal length was found a significant parameter that can affect the accuracy of the model when compared with experimental results. It should be noted that the comparison with numerical results shows that the non-local parameter has minor contribution when the FE model is linear elastic. GREHM was compared to available experimental results and showed accurate estimations of the vertical elastic modulus. Moreover, GREHM was compared to other available homogenisation models and showed better convergence with the experimental data. Therefore, the internal length is an important parameter which should be included in the models.

Table 6

Experimental testing of masonry walls: main parameters of brick units and mortar joints.

Exp. Campaign	Standard	E_b	$t_{b,y}$	$t_{b,x}$	w^*	E_m	$t_{m,y}$	$t_{m,x}$	ℓ	E_{exp}	E_v	f_{exp}
		[MPa]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[MPa]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]
¹ BRE1	EN [†]	1530	55	250	110	1545	10	10	8	2035	2067	13.5
¹ BRE2		1530	55	250	110	1365	10	10	12	2310	2280	13.2
² BOF1	ASTM [‡]	1122	61	257	126	149	13	13	3	743	743	2.9
² BOF2		1122	61	254	125	149	13	13	3.2	767	762	3.1
² BOF3		1122	61	258	126	149	13	13	3.4	785	780	3.0
² BOF4		1224	49	265	129	143	13	13	6.7	1120	1121	2.5
² BOF5		1224	49	259	125	143	13	13	6.7	1091	1121	2.8
² BOF6		2215	46	251	131	143	13	13	5.1	1225	1220	2.7
³ DRO1	EN [†]	4200	45	290	140	125	10	10	1	729	738	12.0
³ DRO2		4200	45	290	140	225	10	10	1	1181	1195	13.7
⁴ FRT1	EN [†]	7500	40	65	40	220	20	20	3	878	874	9.0
⁴ FRT2		7500	40	65	40	220	10	10	3	1938	2000	3.9
⁵ GUM1	EN [†]	3372	75	230	105	5450	12.5	14	15	4824	4883	8
⁵ GUM2		3372	75	230	105	7083	12.5	14	19	5232	5248	9.4
⁵ GUM3		3372	75	230	105	8568	12.5	14	17	5024	5068	12.2
⁶ HOS	ASTM [‡]	12,930	36	123	60	3270	10	10	0.2	8000	8064	18.2
⁷ LLO1	EN [†]	13,595	140	290	70	7976	10	10	7	15,047	15,060	20.4
⁷ LLO2		13,595	140	290	70	5102	10	10	0.1	10,958	12,284	12.3
⁷ LLO3		4003	140	290	45	7976	10	10	40	6042	5999	14.4
⁷ LLO4		4003	140	290	45	5102	10	10	40	5964	5998	11.1
⁸ NWO1	ASTM [‡]	8490	72	224	106	3900	10	10	2	8410	8370	13.5
⁸ NWO2		8490	72	224	106	3450	10	10	0	7210	7206	11.5
⁸ NWO3		8490	72	224	106	750	10	10	4	6610	6670	10.6
⁹ OLI	ASTM [‡]	12,000	45	285	130	4200	10	10	1.1	10,000	9972	28.6
¹⁰ RED1	IS [§]	8000	100	305	143	6600	6	6	0.1	7800	7930	3.2
¹⁰ RED2		8000	100	305	143	6600	12	12	0.1	7200	7846	3.3
¹⁰ RED3		8000	100	305	143	6600	20	20	0.1	7100	7748	3.5
¹⁰ RED4		8000	100	305	143	6600	30	30	0.1	6900	7646	3.6
¹¹ VER	NNI	16,700	52	210	100	2100	13	13	0.1	6800	7063	-

1 [89], 2 [90], 3 [58], 4 [91], 5 [92], 6 [93], 7 [94], 8 [95], 9 [85], 10 [96], 11 [97].

† [98–100], ‡ [101–103], § [104], || [105–107], * w is the wall thickness.

Fig. 16. Comparison of vertical elastic modulus E_v between the proposed GREHM and the models of Taliercio [66], Di Nino and Luongo [62], and Pande et al. [59] for the considered experimental values E_{exp} ; the red dashed lines at $\pm 10\%$ (for the experiments see Table 6). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 17. A comparison between GREHM and the models of Taliercio [66], Di Nino and Luongo [62], and Pande et al. [59] for the elastic modulus in the horizontal direction E_h , the shear modulus G and the Poisson ratio ν_{xy} .

Fig. 18. Total error for GREHM using a unified internal length across the considered experiments (see Table 6) and corresponding values for the other models [59,62,66].

The magnitude of this non-local parameter was found to be of the scale of mortar joint thickness to account for local phenomena in the micro-structure; this value is larger for tested walls involving traditional masonries where local phenomena take place in a wider scale (e.g. high porous mortars). Specifically, limited comparisons show that there is a relation between the internal length ℓ and the porosity of the mortars. An ad-hoc value for the internal length is proposed to be used where there are no other data calibrated on the available experimental data. Normalised graphs are finally provided to facilitate the estimation of the orthotropic properties.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Leonidas Alexandros S. Kouris: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing - original draft. **Dionysios A. Bournas:** Writing - review & editing, Supervision. **Olufemi T. Akintayo:** Writing - review & editing. **Avraam A. Konstantinidis:** Writing - review & editing. **Elias C. Aifantis:** Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. 19. Comparison between GREHM (using the ad hoc ℓ value of Eq. (22)), the homogenisation models and the codes expression (EC6 and ACI530-11) (for the experiments see Table 6).

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Appendix A

The estimation of the vertical homogenised elastic modulus E_v' using the 'exact' arrangement shown at the top of Fig. 5 should take into account additionally the two mortar head joints binding vertically the RSE. The stiffness of the 'core' is given by Eq. (11). The core and the two head joints are in parallel. Therefore, in analogy to Eq. (13a) the 'exact' stiffness is:

$$k_c = k_{b,y} + 2k_{mh,y} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $k_{mh,y}$ is the stiffness of the two head joints with a length $t_{b,y} + t_{m,y}$ and cross section area $t_{m,x}$. Then, Eq. (11) can be applied using k_c instead of $k_{b,y}$. The new homogenised value E_v' should be:

$$E'_c = \frac{t_{b,y}k_c}{(t_{b,x} + t_{m,x})}$$

$$E'_v = t_{tot,y} \frac{E'_c E_m}{2(t_{m,y}/2)^* E'_c + t_{b,y}^* E_m} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

A numerical example is given below comparing the two different elastic moduli. Common values are selected for brick and mortar joints: a brick unit with in-plane dimensions $t_{b,x} = 215$ mm and $t_{b,y} = 65$ mm and mortar joints $t_{m,x} = 10$ mm and $t_{m,y} = 10$ mm in both directions are assumed. The adopted elastic moduli are $E_b = 1500$ GPa and $E_m = 1000$ GPa for brick and mortar respectively. Applying Eq. (12):

$$E_v = (65 + 10) \frac{1500 \cdot 100}{2(t_{m,y}/2)^* 1500 + t_{b,y}^* 1000} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where the gradient lengths are:

$$(t_{m,y}/2)^* = 5 \left[1 - \frac{\ell}{5} \tanh\left(\frac{5}{\ell}\right) \right]$$

$$(t_{b,y})^* = 65 \left[1 - \frac{\ell}{65} \tanh\left(\frac{65}{\ell}\right) \right] \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Applying Eq. (8a):

$$k_{b,y} = \frac{E_b t_{b,x}}{t_{b,y}^*} = \frac{1500 \cdot 215}{t_{b,y}^*}$$

$$k_{m,y} = \frac{E_m t_{b,x}}{(t_{m,y}/2)^*} = \frac{1000 \cdot 215}{(t_{m,y}/2)^*}$$

$$k_{mh,y} = \frac{E_m (t_{m,x}/2)}{(t_{b,y} + t_{m,y})^*} = \frac{1000 \cdot 5}{(t_{b,y} + t_{m,y})^*} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Finally applying Eqs. (11), (A.1) and (A.2) the E_v' is estimated. A plot of the difference between E_v and E_v' is given in for values of ℓ ranging from 0 to 15 mm showing that this can vary from 1 to 2% approximately for this wall (see Fig. A1).

Fig. A1. The difference between E_v and E_v' vs. the internal length.

Appendix B. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2020.110311>.

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